

NEW TEXTILE PREFORMS AND PROCESSING CONCEPTS FOR THE MANUFACTURE OF LOW-COST THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE COMPONENTS

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SUMMARY: Newly developed thermoplastic textile preforms for composite production containing matrix material and reinforcement fibers in a non-impregnated form appear very favorable in view of the general urge for cost reduction. An attempt has been made to develop tools for predicting the forming behavior of a weft-inserted warp knitted sample textile of this type. Good agreement was found between experiment and simulation for in-plane deformation, where even the loading-unloading hysteresis could be modeled. Moreover, the molding concept QUIKTEMP is presented shortly. It allows for the conduction of the whole composite part production in one mold, while being economically reasonable.

KEYWORDS: textile preform, warp knitting, split-film, weft inserts, drapeability, shaping, shear deformation, modeling, QUIKTEMP mold, fast heating and cooling

INTRODUCTION

A strong urge to reduce the weight of transportation vehicles can currently be observed in the automotive, aerospace and railway industry, respectively. At the same time the market conditions and the available budgets put tight limits on the acceptable cost. In particular, any design that is more costly than the conventional ones is not likely to progress into large scale applications.

Composites appear to belong to the materials of choice when replacers for the state-of-the-art steel constructions are discussed. As far as the mass applications are concerned only thermoplastic matrix composites will be able to compete. The requirements of the respective industries in regard to the maximum cycle time in mass applications apparently cannot be met with the currently available thermoset resins.

As pointed out above only composite material solutions with a considerably lowered cost have a chance in the tough competition. For this reason, several recent developments focused on the reduction of the material cost, when compared to the composite materials that have been known mainly from aerospace applications in the past two decades. Two principal approaches can be observed: On the one hand, work is directed towards the use of less costly fibers and matrix materials, respectively, such as glass fibers and polypropylene matrices, for instance. On the other hand efforts are undertaken to reduce the processing cost all along the

way from the constituent production to the composite part. Particularly the development of new textile preforms has attracted much interest.

Since it is hardly economical to place single fibers in order to produce a composite part, it is evident that in most cases some kind of preform will be employed. When continuous fiber reinforced composites are considered textile preforms have been proven in the past to be very favorable. Textile manufacture and processing has been known for centuries and can be applied in mass production at a very low cost and high productivity, respectively.

"DRY IMPREGNATED" TEXTILE PREFORMS - MATERIALS AND PROCESSING

In this paper we are concerned with textile preforms that contain both the reinforcement fibers and the matrix material of the composite to be made. However, unlike in many other preforms such as pre-impregnated sheets, in the cases considered the material is unconsolidated and the matrix polymer is present merely in its original form, i.e. as textile yarn, as powder that adheres to the textile or similar. It should be noted that the matrix yarns can have any cross sectional shape (that is, also split-films are covered by this term, which will be explained later) or length. The textile can thus be seen as a "dry mixture" of the reinforcement fibers and the matrix.

According to the underlying philosophy, impregnation of these textile preforms would be achieved when the final composite part is produced. The processing of the material (after the textile manufacture) would thus be reduced to one step to be conducted in a press. This bears a considerable technical and economical potential:

- reduced preform material cost, since no impregnation of the preform is needed
- reduced production cost, due to the absence of pre-consolidation and other intermediate steps
- availability of the full drapability of the dry textile preform, which facilitates the production of complex shapes

As far as the second point is concerned it should be noted that conventional thermoplastic prepregs are usually pre-compacted in a double-belt press in order to obtain organosheets and to complete the pre-impregnation. This machinery needs a very high invest, while the production rate is not of infinite magnitude. Efforts to significantly reduce the cost of the thermoplastic prepreg-material thus suffer from inherent, tight constraints.

Various techniques to combine matrix material and reinforcement fibers in a textile without pre-impregnation have been considered in the past:

1. Techniques that combine matrix and reinforcement fiber before the manufacture of a textile
 - commingled rovings incorporating thermoplastic staple yarns (air-textured, friction-spun etc. [1]) processed with any textile technique
 - commingled rovings incorporating continuous thermoplastic yarns (on-line assembled) processed with any textile technique
 - FIT ('fibres impregnées thermoplastiques': powder coated reinforcement yarns)
 - other
2. Techniques that combine matrix and reinforcement yarn by the textile processing
 - co-woven structures (conventional thermoplastic yarns or other)
 - co-knitted structures (conventional thermoplastic yarns, thermoplastic split-film etc.)
 - other (stitch-bonding of nonwovens etc.)

The first group cited usually gives a more homogenous distribution of matrix and reinforcement fibers, respectively, already in the textile preform. This most likely yields an even fiber distribution in the eventual composite. It should be noted at this point that during most processes (impregnation/consolidation) the fibers do not move over long distances, especially when short cycle times are considered, due to the viscosity of the molten matrix and the absence of a driving pressure gradient. Especially the now commercially available TWINTEX-roving (by Vetrotex S.A.) has recently attracted interest. Textile structures produced with this roving were transformed to composite parts without substantial problems in many applications. Minor potential problems arising from the shrinkage of the thermoplastic constituents of the roving are pointed out in [2].

The second group of techniques usually is favorable for the lower preform cost achievable with it, since yet one processing step less is needed. However, care has to be taken in order to ensure adequate impregnation when short cycle times are considered. The selection of fiber-matrix-systems with low melt viscosity and good wetting behavior is thus mandatory. It is also necessary to optimize the textile architecture for an even fiber distribution i.e. without matrix rich regions in the composite.

A development falling in the second group is currently carried out by the authors together with multiple partners in the context of an international consortium. While the presentation of this project is not the aim of the current paper, a short introduction should be given, since the deformation behavior of a type of material like developed there shall be considered. A comprehensive report can be found elsewhere [2, 3].

The basic idea is to produce a preform that combines both the matrix material in the form of split-film and the reinforcement rovings. Split-film is a special term for continuous thermoplastic film that has been cut lengthwise into tapes of small cross section. The resultant yarn is much less expensive than conventional (i.e. spun) fibers, but nevertheless well-suited to classical textile operations. Warp knitting of split-film only has been known for a long time as a favorable technique to produce low-cost net-type textile structures in large volumes. Warp knits also exhibit a great drapability. For this reason it was intended to combine warp knitting with weft-inserted reinforcement fibers to obtain a structure like the one displayed in figure 5 (see third section), hence a non-crimp fabric. In the (uniaxial) version shown the loops are made from split-film and melt away during composite production. This textile comprised a tricot loop-structure of polypropylene split-film and weft-inserted glass-rovings with a commercial composite sizing.

DEFORMATION BEHAVIOR OF THE TEXTILE PREFORM

As described above, one fundamental treat of the intended processing route is that the dry, non-molten fabric be inserted in the final compression step where the composite part is formed. Clearly, this gives a much larger formability of the fabric when being compared to a pre-consolidated organosheet. This is especially true when the melting of the matrix thermoplastic does not take place before the material is put in the mold in order to be formed to the final part shape. The latter is incorporated in a process according to the QUIKTEMP concept as described below.

Nevertheless, it is crucial that the textile is not susceptible to wrinkling in large deformation states. The occurrence of folds and wrinkles constitutes a process limit, since this is not acceptable in terms of part quality. Hence, special attention has to be given to this subject.

At this point it should be noted that complex shaping operations nearly always involve large local shear deformations. This deformation mode is likely to yield wrinkling of the fabric [4] and, therefore, needs to be examined in depth. Figure 1 shows the classical deformation of a rectangular piece of fabric by deep-drawing with a spherical punch. As indicated, extensive shear deformation is encountered in the corners of the textile. This example is to show that virtually all deforming processes of initially flat materials into doubly curved surfaces yield large-angle shearing.

Fig. 1: Shaping of a piece of fabric over a spherical surface; large local shear deformation is encountered

In-plane axial deformations, on the other hand, are often not so critical, since substantial pre-tensioning is usually applied by clamps at the fabric edges or other devices. The resulting biaxial stress states then merely exhibit positive stress values (tension) in both directions and thus exclude wrinkling, which is mainly caused by the presence of zero or compressive stresses/strains in the respective directions.

It should also be mentioned that the reinforcement textiles in questions often exhibit a shear rigidity of some two or three orders of magnitude lower than the axial stiffnesses in the direction of the reinforcement fibers, due to a large content of oriented yarn portions in the textile. Inevitably, in deformations without severe constraints that prescribe the local strains (i.e. far away from the clamped edges) the shear mode is much easier activated than the axial deformation modes. This underlines the necessity to be especially concerned with the shear behavior of these textiles. It should be defined more clearly that this reasoning addresses the shearing obtained by the relative rotation one or more initially inclined (to each other) fiber families about the cross-over points. This mode is, for instance, encountered in a lattice-like textile architecture in trellis shear or similar.

For completeness also the bending of the textile preform should be addressed. It is very difficult to access the behavior of fabrics in this deformation mode. Moreover, the bending radii in technical shaping operation are rarely so small that they fall into the range where buckling-out of the textile constituents (i.e. reinforcement rovings) is a problem. Since the biaxial curvature loadcases to a large extent result in local shear as already pointed out, we choose to neglect the bending rigidity and to assume a membrane-like behavior for the moment.

The deformation behavior of the preforms certainly is largely dependent on the specific textile architecture. Figure 2 shows a warp knitted structure in comparison to a woven. Generally it can be said that knitted fabrics are less susceptible to wrinkling than wovens, since their loop structure can accommodate large deformations much more easily [2, 4]. This seems to apply even for uni- or multiaxial weft-inserted warp knits (as shown in figure 3), where the biaxial versions (not shown explicitly) resemble woven structures to a certain extent. Apparently the absence of interlocking of the reinforcement rovings in these non-crimp fabrics is favorable especially in regard to the shear behavior [4]. Ongoing work of the authors is directed to this aspect.

Fig. 2: Woven (a) vs. warp knitted fabric (b)

As a consequence of the above we are mainly concerned with the shear behavior of the textile preforms in question. For the simplicity of the experimental setup we choose to deal with the trellis shear mode (compare the schematic sketch of the device in figure 4). It should be stressed at this point that this mode has to be clearly distinguished from both pure shear and simple shear, as indicated e.g. by Hearle et al. [5]. Only for small deformations the respective shear resistances might be coincident. Our eventual objective is to develop a model that can be employed to predict the forming behavior. However, for this purpose the trellis shear test is just as good as another one, since the specific setup can be incorporated in a finite element model and the textile model parameters then be adjusted to fit the experimental curve.

Nevertheless, in the case of a trellis shear test care has to be taken that the reinforcement fiber families in the textile are exclusively parallel to the ankles of the trellis, when the resistance to relative rotation of the fiber families is to be measured. Otherwise a considerable axial stretch of at least one family of fibers would be the consequence (compare e.g. [6]), resulting in a greatly increased deformation force that is rarely encountered in practical three-dimensional forming operations. This would prohibit the measurement of the shear resistance as intended. Hence, the trellis shear test with the current objective is only applicable to uniaxially and biaxially reinforced textiles such as wovens or warp knits with uni- or biaxial weft-insertion. For multiaxially weft-inserted warp-knits a setup as proposed by Hörsting [4] is needed.

Fig. 3: Weft-inserted warp knit for composite applications; straight inserts are reinforcement rovings; 90°-direction is weft

shear angle on, which depends on the very textile structure. From this critical shear angle on a sharp rise of the deformation force is usually observed [4].

Fig. 4: Trellis shear setup, schematic sketch

thermoplastic loops. The textile stiffness along the rovings is basically determined by the reinforcement fiber modulus and can easily be obtained by taking into account the fineness of the rovings and the number of rovings per unit length.

MODELING THE TEXTILE IN TRELIS SHEAR AND IN TENSION

An attempt was made to model the in-plane deformation behavior of a sample textile, where a uniaxial weft-inserted warp knit was chosen for this work. One major objective was to model also the hysteresis in the shear deformation properly. The out-of plane behavior, that is to say the behavior in 3-dimensional deformations, will be subject of future activities. However, no

Figure 5 shows the fabric considered in this study in the initial and in a deformed state. This very fabric is actually not a development of the cited project. It is, however, of very similar type and was used for the experiments reported here. It is clearly visible that the rovings come close to each other as the deformation progresses. Like in the shearing of other (woven and weft-inserted) fabrics, this leads to blocking of the deformation from a certain

The resulting force-deformation curves of the trellis shear test carried out are given together with the simulation results in the next section's figures. Due to the specific setup at the time of the conduction of the experiments only positive displacements x of the trellis load lower joint (versus the upper support) could be achieved. In figure 7, for example, the loading and unloading curve are given. An extensive hysteresis identifies a considerable inter-loop and loop-roving friction during shear deformation. The contribution of the respective effects will hardly be separable and are, therefore, only accounted for in a cumulative manner in the modeling.

Aside from the shear experiments uniaxial tensile tests were conducted to explore the in-plane axial stiffnesses. However, the experiments were limited to the direction perpendicular to the reinforcement rovings in order to measure the stiffness of the

principal problems should arise in using the same model, since apart from the out-of-plane bending the fundamental deformation modes are equal.

We will at first be concerned with the adequate representation of the shear behavior and then show that the model with the same set of parameters is also valid for the tensile test in the loop direction (warp). Standard finite element techniques are applied in all cases. For convenience the ankles of the trellis shear tester were modeled by very stiff beams in order to prescribe the trellis shear kinematics. Since a homogeneous deformation field was found in the experiments it was chosen for the sake of a low numerical expense to model only a smaller portion of the textile (square of size $10 \times 10 \text{ mm}^2$ in, while the shear tester was a square of ca. $170 \times 170 \text{ mm}^2$).

In the setup chosen the reinforcement rovings are represented by standard Euler-Bernoulli beam elements. Figure 6 shows the model. Apparently substantial friction is encountered in the loops and between loops and rovings as the deformation progresses (compare the experimentally observed hysteresis in figure 7). The thermoplastic loops were thus modeled by rods with non-linear force-extension behavior. Since the numerous friction effects occurring can hardly be separated it was decided to represent the loop volume between the reinforcement rovings by pairs of mutually orthogonal elastic-plastic rods with a certain work hardening rule, all inclined with respect to the roving direction (compare figure 6, where only half of the rods is actually elastic-plastic; the rest is elastic for the sake of computation time reduction).

In the case currently considered the location and orientation of the rods must not necessarily coincide with the loop yarns. The elastic-plastic material parameters were adjusted so that the macroscopically observed non-linear force-displacement curve with hysteresis was met. However, during this process it was found that the rather steep slope of the curve at large shear angles could never be modeled. Hence, when the small-angle shear part of the curve was fit, the rigidity given by the model was much too low for large shear angles, whereas a fitting of the large-angle shear resulted in considerably larger rigidity predictions in the low range than given by the experimental values.

Fig. 5: Undeformed ($x=0 \text{ mm}$) and deformed ($x=65 \text{ mm}$) fabric state; loops from polypropylene split-film, weft-inserted glass rovings (initial spacing: 1.9 mm)

Fig. 6: Finite element model assembled from linear elastic beams, elastic-plastic (and linear elastic) rods and an especially developed 'orthogonal stiffness' element

Physically this effect is related to the compression of the loop system (and to a certain extent to the compression of the rovings, dependent on the textile's parameters), that yields 'blocking' of the deformation when the rovings come very close to each other at large shear angles, as pointed out already above. However, any rod that is fixed to nodes on the beam elements representing the reinforcement rovings, regardless of the original orientation, cannot display this increase of stiffness orthogonal to the rovings. The projected stiffness of the rod in this direction will rather decrease, since a continuous inclination takes place as the shear progresses. This is a fundamental conflict resulting from the formulation of a finite element model with the available standard elements.

Therefore, a special finite element was developed, which, in a qualitative manner, precisely displays the compressional stiffness of the loop volume orthogonal to the rovings. With proper parameters this element can also display the tension behavior of the loop system. The representation of the axial stiffness orthogonal to the rovings is then exclusively taken over by the 'orthogonal stiffness' element, whereas the elastic-plastic rods are adjusted so that the model as a whole is in accordance with the textile's shear behavior. The tensile behavior of the textile in the roving direction is represented by the axial stiffness of the respective beam elements. Details on the 'orthogonal stiffness' element will be given in a detailed publication which is currently being prepared [7].

Figure 7 shows the results of experiment and simulation in one diagram. Apparently the agreement is very good, even for the unloading curve, which is subject to extensive hysteresis. The model with identical parameters was also tested for its behavior in tension orthogonal to the roving direction. The predicted force-displacement curve is shown in figure 8 together with the corresponding experimental curve. Again, experiment and simulation agree very well. In this example, the stiffness value of the 'orthogonal stiffness' elements accumulated over the specimen width was close to the rigidity of the real specimen in this direction, hence these elements represented the major part of the model tensile stiffness orthogonal to the rovings and at the same time modeled the loop compression in shearing properly.

Fig. 7: Loading and unloading force-displacement curve in trellis shear; experiment and simulation in comparison

Fig. 8: Fabric in uniaxial tension orthogonal to the rovings; load-displacement curve of experiment and simulation in comparison

For obvious reasons it would be favorable to have a continuous representation (i.e. shell or membrane finite elements) of the fabrics considered. However, with the high degree of anisotropy, in particular the extremely low shear rigidity and a poisson contraction behavior that is typically far from anything known from continuous solids, at this points it seems questionable to the authors whether this will be achievable in the near future, when not some of the accuracy requirements are dropped. The combined beam/truss representation on the other hand appears to be an interesting alternative. The incorporation into larger models and complex shaping simulations have to be investigated in the near future.

FAST HEATING AND COOLING OF THE MATERIAL IN MASS PRODUCTION: THE QUIKTEMP CONCEPT

Thermoplastic composites are usually processed by heating the material up externally and then pressing it in a cold mold. An uncontrolled, quick cooling of the part is inevitable, which may limit the quality of impregnation and might result in a material with poor mixing of the constituents. On top of that the transfer from the preheating station to the press may cause trouble particularly with 'dry' textile preforms. They may suffer from shrinkage of the thermoplastic constituents and increased void formation in the ready part, as there is no lateral pressure or mechanical support during transfer [3].

Hence, favorably the complete process would be conducted in one mold. This, however, would require the mold to go through the same thermal history as the part, which is not feasible with state-of-the-art molds due to their excessive thermal inertia. The consequence would be cycle times on the order of hours which are prohibitive in mass production.

Fig. 9: QUIKTEMP - Newly developed mold design for fast heating and cooling

The design shown in figure 9 incorporates the finding that domains of the mold volume other than the cavity surface region can be of different temperature. Hence, the mold consists of a large volume made of a material with high thermal inertia (e.g. steel) and a smaller volume of very low thermal inertia.

While the first region acts as a heat storage and is held at a very high temperature level (e.g. 300 or 400 °C) the second region - termed "forming region" - is in contact with the part. It comprises heating and cooling systems which adjust the temperature of the cavity surface to the desired value. During the heating phase there will be an additional heat flux from the heat storage into the forming region as a significant temperature gradient exists in this direction. This boosts the heating.

During cooling the heat storage tends to decelerate the temperature change. However, as the cooling is by far more effective this is not really of concern when considering the total cycle time. Potential problems can be overcome by raising the coolant volume flux.

The newly developed QUIKTEMP concept works properly, which was shown by tests with a lab-scale mold [3]. It allows for heating and cooling rates up to 200°C per minute. Merits of

QUIKTEMP are i.e. the continuous application of pressure throughout the whole cycle and the free choice of the temperature history, while reasonable cycle times on the order of minutes can be maintained. Many of the problems mentioned above can thus be avoided. For a detailed presentation of the concept, compare [3].

CONCLUSIONS

Non-impregnated textiles incorporating both matrix material and reinforcement fibers that are suitable to be processed in one step in order to obtain a composite are very attractive costwise when compared to conventional thermoplastic prepregs. They are especially well suited to accommodate complex part shapes without substantial wrinkling, where their low shear resistance seems of fundamental importance.

A finite element model for the simulation of one textile of this kind, a weft-inserted warp knit, in fundamental in-plane deformation modes was presented. The model fits corresponding experimental results very well. The QUIKTEMP concept for fast heating and cooling of molds was presented. It can favorably be applied also in mass applications in conjunction with the textile preforms considered.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank Engtex AB, Mulsjö, Sweden, for providing the textile material. The material was taken from a preliminary test production for the Brite-Euram Project BE7256-93 before its actual start. That project is funded by the European Commission under the Contract No. BRE2-CT94-0552. The financial contribution is gratefully acknowledged.

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